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COMPARISON OF SHORT CARBON AND POLY(P-PHENYLENE-2,6-BENZOBISOXAZOLE) FIBERS ON THE PROPERTIES OF POLYESTER THERMOPLASTIC ELASTOMERS

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Introduction

- Thermoplastic Elastomers combine the benefits of toughness and flexibility of traditional thermosetting rubbers with the processability and ability to be remolded and recycled of thermoplastics
- Poly(p-phenylene-2,6-benzobisoxazole) (PBO) is a high-strength thermosetting polymer with additional benefits of improved abrasion resistance, and excellent fatigue resistance
- Comparison of Carbon and PBO fibers is interesting because despite having similar base mechanical properties their resulting composites perform differently

Structure of PBO Fiber

Materials and Fabrication

- Thermoplastic polyester elastomer (DuPont Hytrel 5556) with hardness shore D 55 was used as the matrix material
- Composites were prepared by twin screw compounding followed by fabrication of the samples by injection molding

Matrix Material	Reinforcing Filler	Fiber Weight %	Fiber Volume %	Nomenclature
Hytrel 5556	PBO	5	3.9	TPEE 5PBO
		10	7.8	TPEE 10PBO
	Carbon Fiber	5	3.3	TPEE 5CF
		10	6.8	TPEE 10CF
	Neat			TPEE

Fiber	Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Pre-Processing length (mm)
PBO	270	5.8	3
Carbon	242	4.1	3

Thermal Properties (TGA and DSC)

— TPEE — TPEE 5CF — TPEE 10CF — TPEE 5PBO — TPEE 10PBO

— TPEE — TPEE 5CF — TPEE 10CF — TPEE 5PBO — TPEE 10PBO

Mechanical Properties in Tension

Investigation of Fiber Length

Conclusions and Future Work

- Both carbon and PBO provide excellent reinforcement in terms of modulus to the elastomeric matrix
- Hypothesized that a combination of fiber length and interfacial adhesion result in superior strength of PBO fiber reinforced composites
- Due to being ductile in nature there is much less fiber breakage during processing in the PBO fibers resulting in longer fiber length
- Future work is to investigate the interfacial properties for both fiber types as well as the 3D fiber structure